

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR OVERCOMING PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH COMPETENCIES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical foundations of developing the structural components of students' speech competence in native language teaching. It examines the scientific views of linguists and methodologists on enhancing oral and written speech, expressing independent thoughts, fostering a creative approach to text creation, and mastering speech culture.

Keywords: speech, oral and written literacy, speech skills, speech competence, exercise, learning task, work on the text.

In recent years, the primary goal of native language lessons in our republic has been defined as nurturing well-rounded individuals who think independently and creatively, can express their thoughts fluently both orally and in writing, and comprehend the ideas of others. Normative foundations are being developed to improve the methodology for enhancing the speech competencies of upper-grade students. The priority has been set to "educate independent thinkers with firm life perspectives, loyal to the homeland, and to increase their social activity in the process of deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society." [Юсупова, 2005:56]. As a result, opportunities for improving the methodology of developing students' speech competencies in general secondary education institutions will expand.

The unique role of speech competencies is crucial in enhancing the quality and effectiveness of native language lessons. It is essential for students to complete exercises independently, draw correct conclusions from sentences and text content, retell the main idea understood from a text through listening, and express themselves orally and in writing based on literary language norms. The ability to freely articulate thoughts in both spoken and written forms is a necessary skill. Indeed, "We mobilize all the strength and resources of our state and society to ensure that our youth grow into individuals who think independently, possess high intellectual and moral potential, and can compete with their peers worldwide in every field, achieving happiness in life." [Mirziyoyev, 2016:14], – This recognition places a vital and urgent task before the methodology of native language teaching: to cultivate competitive and knowledgeable individuals who can rival youth worldwide, comprehend various forms of information through listening,

express their thoughts meaningfully and clearly, convey ideas in a rich and precise manner, read attentively, adhere to orthographic rules in writing, analyze information critically, and draw relevant conclusions while maintaining their own informed stance.

In N. Sh. Turdiyev's guide "Umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim texnologiyalari" the concepts of "competence" and "competency" are described with a focus on the practical application of knowledge. It is recommended to consider the integration of knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure an individual's professional activity, as well as the targeted emotional and volitional strength of the individual.

Additionally, in the methodology guide *"Methods of Teaching the Uzbek Language"* by B. To'xliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, and T. Ziyodova, it is stated: "Native language lessons cultivate knowledge, skills, and abilities for mastering and effectively utilizing the art of speech. In this process, speech culture is developed. Speech culture teaches youth the etiquette of communication, from simple daily greetings to understanding the nuances of addressing whom, for what purpose, when, where, and how. It also plays a significant role in comprehending the principles of Eastern etiquette and the art of eloquent recitation." [To'xliyev, 2006: 314] This clearly indicates that the primary task of native language lessons is to enhance students' speech culture, communicative skills, independent, creative, and logical thinking, as well as to develop their ability to participate in communication by using meaningful and contextually appropriate words in various speech situations. Professor Sh.Yusupova emphasizes that in native language lessons, different objectives can be pursued by applying the "Interpretation Method" to improve students' oral and written speech.

1. Interpretation helps students comprehend the theoretical information covered in native language lessons.
2. Interpretation refers to the application of theoretical knowledge in practice.
3. It helps develop oral speech skills.
4. It harmonizes the relationship between orthophonic and orthographic norms.
5. Throughout the entire lesson process, theoretical knowledge is emphasized for the students".

As the methodologist scholar correctly noted, in native language lessons, as a result of students interpreting theoretical knowledge, their skills and competencies in speaking correctly, pronouncing words according to speech techniques, and writing correctly while adhering to literary language norms are tested. The level at which they apply the knowledge gained during the lesson to practical situations is also evaluated.

In native language lessons, the development of speech competencies is primarily related to how effectively the teacher organizes the lesson. Speech competencies such as

listening comprehension, hearing, reading, and writing are continuously developed in almost every native language lesson. One of the key tasks of the teacher in language education is to monitor the development indicators of the speech skills formed in students and, at the same time, identify any areas where their speech competencies are lacking. The teacher should use interactive methods and consistently address the mistakes and shortcomings students make, correcting these gaps in a timely manner.

The goal is to teach students to work with spelling dictionaries, practice dictation exercises, and encourage them to memorize and learn the correct spelling of words. It also involves working with explanatory dictionaries to understand the semantic structure of words and using synonym and antonym dictionaries. To achieve this, the teacher should allocate time at the end of the lesson and place particular emphasis on reading and writing exercises. This will help improve speech competencies. Certainly, this process requires the teacher to go beyond using just a textbook, engaging in research, consulting additional scientific literature, and applying modern and advanced methods.

The importance of the teacher's serious approach to developing students' speech competencies is highlighted in the research of Sh.Sariyev. He states: *"Based on the teacher's reading example, students learn to read correctly and expressively. To read a text in class, the teacher must be well-prepared, strive for a deeper understanding of the content, and determine how certain parts of the text should be read. After explaining how to read specific sounds, syllables, and words, the teacher should have students read the text in turn. The teacher monitors them and provides corrections as needed"*.

If the teacher teaches students to read words as they are in the example, pays attention to intonation and stress while reading words, and ensures that the lexical units in sentences are pronounced clearly and fluently, the students' reading technique will transition into an active state.

Based on the views expressed in scientific and methodological literature by researchers, the term "developing speech competencies" is explained as follows: It refers to the knowledge, skills, and abilities that result from a student's mastery of lexical, grammatical, word formation, syntactic, and stylistic norms in their speech during native language lessons. This includes their ability to effectively apply listening comprehension, reading, speaking, and writing skills in appropriate and practical ways in various speech situations. It also involves forming a subjective attitude towards events and phenomena in social life, maintaining a firm stance in different speech processes, and achieving a high level of development in both oral and written speech.

One of the key factors in improving the methodology for developing speech competencies in native language lessons is the focus on developing both oral and written speech based on the norms of literary language through communicative, innovative, and

creative approaches. This aspect is closely related to the collective nature of educational activities and the thorough assimilation of knowledge. It involves acquiring speech skills, such as listening comprehension, hearing, speaking, and writing, as well as the ability to express subjective opinions. It also includes monitoring the competencies and abilities related to these skills, taking into account the learner's aspirations, abilities, and conclusions drawn from life experiences, all of which are manifested in various speech situations.

After reviewing the textbooks, it can be concluded that, based on the development of students' speech competencies, the full development of students' ability to speak freely in native language lessons has not been achieved. Furthermore, students are not sufficiently skilled in using various language levels, such as lexical, morphological, and syntactic units, in speech situations, nor do they fully master the ability to independently create and write texts in accordance with the norms of literary language. Therefore, in order to develop their speech competencies, it is necessary to teach students to perfectly use the communicative qualities that ensure the cultural aspects of speech in their language.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida" Farmoni.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Erkin va farovon demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. – T.: O'zbekiston.2016. – 14 b.
3. Mahmudov M. Bolalarning o'quv maqsadi– ta'limni ilmiy loyihalash omili// Xalq ta'limi. –2005. –№ 5. – 49 b.
4. Sariyev Sh. U. Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish darslarida matn ustida ishlash orqali nutq o'stirish nazariyasi va amaliyoti (1-, 2-sinf materiallari misolida)): Ped. fan. nomz. diss. –T.:2020.
5. To'xliyev B., Shamsiyeva M., Ziyodova T. O'zbek tili o'qitish metodikasi. –T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2006.
6. Yusupova Sh. J. Ona tili ta'limi samaradorligini oshirish va ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni joriy etish. Ped. Fan. Nom-di diss. - Toshkent: TPDI, 1998.
7. Yusupova Sh. J. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili darslarida o'quvchilar tafakkurini o'stirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari: Ped. fan doktori ... diss.- Toshkent.
8. Hamroyev G'. H. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimida fonetikaga doir o'quv materiallarining metodik ta'minotini takomillashtirish: PhD diss.... – Samarqand.

9. Turdiyev N. Sh., Asadov Y. M., Akbarova S. N., Temirov D. Sh. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim texnologiyalari. - T.: T.N.Qori Niyoziy nomidagi O'zPFITI, 2015.- 8 b.
10. Yo'ldoshev R. A., Mirjalolova L. R. Ona tili ta'limida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv: Metodik qo'llanma. – T.: Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat O'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti, 2019. – 9 b.
11. Qo'yliyeva Sh. *Ona tili ta'limida o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish muammolari*. “Global ta'lim va milliy metodika taraqqiyoti” konferensiya materiallari, Toshkent – 2023-yil, 338-345-betlar